

Understanding the influence of bio-based fertilizers (BBFs) on sorption of pharmaceuticals in soils: Effects of pH and organic matter

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ABSTRACT

Understanding the impact of bio-based fertilizers (BBFs) on the sorption of ionizable pharmaceuticals in soils via both pH and organic matter has received little research attention so far. To address this knowledge gap, we conducted batch sorption experiments with four common ionic pharmaceuticals used in human medicine (naproxen, diclofenac, furosemide, and ibuprofen), four types of commercial BBFs (ash-based, plant-based, animal by-product-based, and manure-based), and two agricultural soils from contrasting climates (Finland and Spain). The sorption affinity of the four pharmaceuticals varied across soil matrices. The addition of BBFs to soil caused modifications in both organic matter content (OMC) and pH levels, which reduced sorption of the pharmaceuticals in soils amended with the ash-based BBF, whereas BBFs rich in organic matter increased sorption. To further quantify the individual contributions of pH and OMC to sorption variation, a normalized sensitivity index (NSI) approach was employed using a sorption model parameterized by pH and OMC. NSI analysis revealed that the sorption of the studied compounds to soil was primarily pH-sensitive at low pH and in low-OMC zones. Dominance maps constructed from NSI values highlighted soil-specific transition zones in which pH or OMC governed sorption behavior in soil. These findings underscore the importance of compound-specific, soil-dependent BBF effects, and suggest that tailored management of soil properties through BBF application may offer effective strategies for mitigating pharmaceutical mobility in agroecosystems.

1. Introduction

In recent decades, the extensive use of human pharmaceuticals and veterinary antibiotics has introduced these substances into soil through various pathways, posing potential risks to soil health (Matongo et al., 2015; Tijani et al., 2016). As a result, the fate of pharmaceuticals in soil has become a topic of growing concern. In parallel, modern agriculture is exploring alternatives to chemical fertilizers, with bio-based fertilizers (BBFs) derived from sources such as manure, plant residues, sewage sludge, and ash-based materials emerging as promising solutions to close nutrient loops and improve soil health (Chojnacka et al., 2020). However, these exogenous substances may influence the fate of pharmaceuticals in soil, particularly through sorption processes, which play a crucial role in determining the fate of organic pollutants by affecting their bioavailability and potential leaching (Kiecak et al., 2019; Xu et al., 2021; Zhang et al., 2021). Thus, understanding how BBFs impact the

sorption behavior of pharmaceuticals in soils is essential.

Unlike non-polar compounds such as PAHs (polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons), pharmaceuticals are often ionizable and can occur in neutral, cationic, anionic, or zwitterionic form depending on their pK_a and the soil pH (Sigmund et al., 2022; Xu et al., 2021). Consequently, their sorption capacity exhibits a pronounced pH dependence, with sorption increasing or decreasing exponentially as speciation changes (Sigmund et al., 2022). For example, anionic pharmaceuticals (e.g., ibuprofen) may be repelled at circumneutral pH but can still sorb via mineral interactions under acidic conditions (Martín et al., 2019). In addition, cationic pharmaceuticals (e.g., atenolol) are strongly retained by negatively charged soil organic matter (SOM) functional groups (Park et al., 2018). Thus, both soil pH and organic matter are central parameters controlling pharmaceutical sorption in soil (Srinivasan et al., 2013; Stromer et al., 2018).

Mechanistic models have been proposed to interpret these effects.

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For instance, the dual-additive model combines contributions from organic carbon and cation-exchange capacity (CEC) to describe the sorption behaviors of cationic pharmaceuticals in soils (Dröge and Goss, 2013), while polyparameter linear free energy relationships (pp-LFERs) predict partitioning of neutral compounds into soil organic matter (Nguyen et al., 2005). BBFs, as complex matrices, can alter soil characteristics such as organic matter content (OMC) and soil pH. Most existing studies, however, focus independently on a single parameter, such as increases in OMC resulting from BBFs (Jiang et al., 2021; Real et al., 2021; Xu et al., 2021), for example showing that olive-mill waste enhanced the sorption of umbelliferone and salicylic acid (Real et al., 2021), or that livestock manure strengthened chlortetracycline retention (Jiang et al., 2021). Yet, how simultaneous BBF-induced changes in OMC and pH jointly affect pharmaceutical sorption remains poorly understood.

To fill this knowledge gap, we conducted batch sorption experiments to study the effects of BBF application on the sorption of selected ionic pharmaceuticals in soils, exploring both OMC and pH as key influencing factors. Furthermore, using the experimental dataset, we established a sorption model to disentangle and quantify the respective contributions of BBF-induced changes in pH and OMC to pharmaceutical sorption behavior. Specifically, we examined four common ionizable pharmaceuticals used in human medicine (naproxen, diclofenac, furosemide, and ibuprofen), four representative types of commercial BBFs (ash-based, plant residue-based, manure-based and animal by-product-based) and two agricultural soils from contrasting climates (Finland and Spain).

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Compounds selection and materials

Naproxen, ibuprofen, diclofenac, and furosemide are pharmaceuticals that are commonly used by humans and have been consistently identified in multiple environmental matrices, including wastewater and soil at $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$ to mg/kg (or $\mu\text{g}/\text{L}$ to mg/L) concentrations (Kümmerer, 2009; Li, 2014). Consequently, our study focused on these four weak acid compounds, employing isotopically labelled internal standards (naproxen-d3, ibuprofen-d3, diclofenac-13C6, and furosemide-d5) for precise quantification. The unlabeled and labelled compounds were procured from Sigma-Aldrich, as detailed in Table S1. The ionization behavior of the selected pharmaceuticals across environmentally relevant pH values is shown in Fig. 2, illustrating the fractions of neutral and ionized species based on their respective pK_a values.

LC-grade solvents including methanol, acetonitrile (ACN), ammonium acetate, sodium azide, and calcium chloride were purchased from Biosolve (Valkenswaard, The Netherlands), and acetic acid was obtained from Merck (Darmstadt, Germany). Milli-Q water was purified with an ELGA water purification system (Veolia Water Technologies Netherlands B.V., Ede, the Netherlands). These reagents were employed in liquid chromatography–tandem mass spectrometry (LC-MS/MS) and sorption experiments. Working mixed standards solutions at $5 \mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ containing all target analytes were prepared by appropriate dilution of the individual stock solutions. Working labelled standard solutions at a concentration of $500 \mu\text{g}/\text{L}$ were prepared in ACN.

2.2. BBFs and soil samples

The four BBFs used in this study, **ADC**, **BA1**, **OG2**, and **FEK** are ash-based, plant-based, animal by-product-based, and manure-based BBFs, respectively, and the two agricultural soil samples originated from Finland and Spain (Das et al., 2023). Further details of the BBFs and soils used are listed in Table S3 and our previous publications (Das et al., 2023; Dong et al., 2023). Soil pH was determined by suspending 5 g of soil in 25 mL of Milli-Q water (1:5, w/v). The mixture was shaken horizontally for 16 h , allowed to settle for 4 h , and the pH of the supernatant

was measured using a Consort C831 pH meter equipped with a VWR Universal pH Electrode (VWR International B.V., Amsterdam, the Netherlands). Measurements were performed in triplicate. For cation exchange capacity (CEC) determination, 4 g of air-dried and sieved ($<2 \text{ mm}$) soil was extracted with 100 mL of 0.125 M BaCl_2 solution. The filtered extracts were analyzed by ICP-OES (PerkinElmer Optima 8000) to quantify exchangeable Ca, Mg, K, Na, Fe, Mn, and Al (Jonkman et al., 2019). CEC was calculated as the sum of these exchangeable metal ions. Measurements were conducted in quadruplicate. Organic matter content (OMC) of BBF samples was determined by loss-on-ignition (LOI). Briefly, 5 g of BBF was dried at $105 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 24 h to obtain the dry weight, followed by combustion at $375 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 16 h . The relative weight loss after combustion was expressed as OMC (Dong et al., 2023).

2.3. Batch sorption experiments

Batch sorption experiments were performed using a modified OECD 106 batch equilibrium method. The experimental design consisted of four groups: (i) two soils, (ii) four BBFs, (iii) mixtures of soils and a BBF at 2% or 5% (dw/dw), and (iv) blank controls. The 5% amendment rate with BBFs was used for analysis of sorption behavior and model building, whereas the 2% amendment rate was used for model verification (see Section 3.5). In each case, 3 g of soil, BBF, or a mixture of BBF and soil were weighed into 50 mL polypropylene centrifuge tubes. The compound mixture, dissolved in ACN, was evaporated to dryness under a gentle stream of nitrogen in a fume hood. The dried residue was subsequently re-dissolved in Milli-Q water containing 0.01 M CaCl_2 and 200 mg L^{-1} NaN_3 to prevent microbial degradation. Each sample was prepared by mixing 30 mL of this aqueous solution with 3 g of soil to reach a soil/solution ratio of 1:10 (kg/L), and spiked with target compounds to reach nominal initial concentrations (C_0) of 0 , 100 , 200 , 500 , 750 , and $1000 \mu\text{g}/\text{L}$. For the blank controls, two types were included: (i) Milli-Q water containing 0.01 M CaCl_2 and 200 mg L^{-1} NaN_3 without spiking, mixed with the sorbents (soil, BBFs, or their mixtures) to determine background concentrations; and (ii) aqueous filtrates obtained from the soil–solution mixtures, into which the target compounds were spiked to assess potential analyte loss during the experimental procedure. Afterwards, all the tubes were continuously shaken and equilibrated for 24 h at $21 \pm 1 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ in the dark as recommended in (Alhalabi et al., 2024), and then centrifuged at $4,000 \times g$ for 10 min to separate the solid and aqueous phases. The decanted solutions were filtered using $0.22 \mu\text{m}$ polypropylene filters and a labelled internal standard (IS) was added before injecting the samples into the LC-MS/MS system to obtain their aqueous phase concentration, C_w ($\mu\text{g}/\text{L}$). The concentration of pharmaceuticals sorbed in soil, C_s ($\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$), was calculated from the measured solution phase concentrations based on mass balance using the equation $C_s = (C_0 - C_w) \times V/m$, where V is the solution volume (L) and m is the dry mass of solids (kg). The background aqueous concentrations of the studied pharmaceuticals in the sorbent–aqueous controls were below the method limit of detection.

2.4. Sorption data processing

The commonly used Freundlich model was employed using the Freundlich equation: $C_s = K_f \times C_w^n$, where K_f is the Freundlich capacity coefficient, ($(\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}) \times (\text{L}/\mu\text{g})^n$), and n (dimensionless) describes the isotherm curvature. The Freundlich equation parameter calculations and fitting were performed using OriginPro 2021. Soil–water distribution coefficient (K_d) values (L/kg), representing sorption affinity, were determined by individual points from the measured data within the tested concentrations via $K_d = C_s/C_w$. NRMSE (Normalized Root Mean

$$\text{Squared Error}) = \frac{\sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \bar{y})^2}}{|y_{\max} - y_{\min}|}$$

2.5. Sorption model with pH and OMC dependency

$$\text{General model : } K_d = f(D_{ow}) + \alpha \times f(\text{OMC}) \quad (1)$$

$$\text{Naproxen : } K_d = 0.38 \times D_{ow} + \alpha \times 0.85 \times \text{OMC}^{1.32} \quad (2)$$

$$\text{Diclofenac : } K_d = 0.05 \times D_{ow} + \alpha \times 2.00 \times \text{OMC}^{1.32} \quad (3)$$

$$\text{Furosemide : } K_d = 0.40 \times D_{ow} + \alpha \times 0.40 \times \text{OMC}^{1.93} \quad (4)$$

$$\text{Ibuprofen : } K_d = 0.008 \times D_{ow} + \alpha \times 0.75 \times \text{OMC}^{1.28} \quad (5)$$

In this study, we investigated four weakly acidic pharmaceuticals, considering both their intrinsic properties and the influence of soil characteristics on sorption. Previous studies have demonstrated that neutral molecules and anionic species interact with soils via distinct mechanisms: for neutral molecules, sorption is mainly governed by hydrophobic interactions, whereas for anions, sorption occurs predominantly at positively charged sites, such as those associated with organic matter, clay, or metal oxides (Alhalabi et al., 2024; Fabregat-Palau et al., 2024; Sigmund et al., 2022; Tülp et al., 2009). Notably, the contribution of metal oxides becomes more pronounced only under low organic carbon (e.g. <1 %) (Tülp et al., 2009). In this study OMC exceeds approximately 3 % for most soils. The addition of BBFs was found to modify both pH and OMC (Table S7). Accordingly, our models focused on these two factors. Changes in pH shift the neutral/anion speciation; the pH-dependence of hydrophobicity was expressed via an exponential relationship using D_{ow} as proxy: $\log D_{ow} = \log P - \log(1 + 10^{\text{pH} - \text{pK}_a})$, following the Henderson–Hasselbalch formulation for weak acids (Hodges et al., 2019; Sigmund et al., 2022). In contrast, anionic sorption capacity was assumed to vary with OMC. We tested three functional forms for each predictor in a general model (Eq (1))—linear ($y = a \times x$), exponential ($y = a \times b^x$), and power ($y = a \times x^b$), and selected models using five-fold cross-validation repeated 20 times to enhance model generalizability and mitigate overfitting. The best performers were chosen based on R^2 and normalized root mean squared error (NRMSE) (Table S13–16 in SI-1). The data are from two regular soils and two soils amended with four types of BBFs (Table S7 and SI-2). Since our experiments covered only a limited but representative range of pH (5.7–8.3) and OMC (3.3–11.4 %), we supplemented our dataset with literature values to broaden environmental coverage (Barron et al., 2009; Durán-Álvarez et al., 2012; Estévez et al., 2014; Li et al., 2020; Lin and Gan, 2011; Mitra and Benfield, 2018; Scheytt et al., 2005; Williams et al., 2009; Xu et al., 2009; Zhang et al., 2017). As a result, the combined dataset spans a wide range of environmental conditions: for naproxen, pH ranged from 5.5 to 9.0 and OMC from 0.1 % to 12.2 %, $n = 229$; for ibuprofen, pH ranged from 4.8 to 9.2 and OMC from 0.1 % to 12.2 %, $n = 247$; for diclofenac, pH ranged from 4.8 to 9.2 and OMC from 0.1 % to 12.2 %, $n = 231$; and for furosemide, pH ranged from 3.2 to 8.3 and OMC from 2.3 % to 12.2 %, $n = 216$ (SI-2). α denotes the speciation factor describing the fraction of the compound present in its anionic form at a given pH, $\alpha = 1/(1 + 10^{\text{pK}_a - \text{pH}})$. To evaluate the relative influence of soil pH and OMC on the sorption (K_d), we employed a normalized sensitivity index (NSI), defined as $\text{NSI}_x = \partial K_d / \partial x \times x / K_d$, where x represents either pH or OMC. This dimensionless index measures the proportional change in K_d resulting from a relative change in the input variable.

2.6. Liquid chromatography–mass spectrometry analysis

High-resolution liquid chromatography coupled to tandem mass spectrometry (LC-MS/MS) analyses were performed on an advanced ultra-high-performance liquid chromatography (UHPLC) system (Nexera, Shimadzu, Den Bosch, The Netherlands) coupled to a Bruker

Daltonics maXis 4G q-ToF/MSMS, equipped with an ESI source and a High-Definition collision cell (Bruker Daltonics, Bremen, Germany). The compounds were separated on a core-shell Kinetex biphenyl column (100 × 2.1 mm, 2.6 μm , 100 Å; Phenomenex, Utrecht, The Netherlands) as described in Das et al. and Albergamo et al. (Albergamo et al., 2018; Das et al., 2023). Mobile phases were water with 0.05 % acetic acid (A) and methanol (B) with the following gradient (B%): 0 min 0 %, 2.5 min 50 %, 5–7 min 100 %, followed by a 4-min re-equilibration to initial conditions (Albergamo et al., 2018). The MS detector was calibrated using a sodium acetate solution in both positive and negative ESI. Furthermore, sodium acetate was also used for the system's recalibration between injections.

Internal calibration curves were constructed by analyzing a dilution range of the standard solution in ultra-pure water. The method for target identification and quantification was fine-tuned based on methods described by Narain-Ford et al. and Albergamo et al. (Albergamo et al., 2018; Narain-Ford et al., 2022). Comprehensive data on the analytes was sourced both in full-scan and through the collision-induced dissociation MS/MS mode, facilitated by TASQ software (Bruker Daltonics). This software offers a dual-stage algorithm that accurately identifies and quantifies analytes, referencing a curated database. Broadband collision-induced dissociation (bbCID) MS/MS, in which all ions are fragmented by alternating low and high collision energy, was used to optimize ion selection and fragmentation data collection of standards.

2.7. Quality assurance and quality control

To demonstrate method performance, we evaluated matrix effects (ME), linearity of the internal calibration curves, method limits of detection and quantification (MLOD/MLOQ), accuracy, and precision (intra-/inter-day). For each analytical batch, a matrix blank was processed alongside the samples to verify at background concentration levels of analytes. Calibration was performed across 0.05–50 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$ (0.05, 0.5, 1, 2.5, 5, 10, 15, 25, and 50 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$). Precision was expressed as relative standard deviation (%RSD), with within-day repeatability and intermediate precision over five separate days both evaluated at 25 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$ (Table S6). ME was characterized using a post-extraction spike approach in triplicates: a blank matrix extract was fortified with known amounts of analytes and analyzed, and the responses were compared with solvent standards prepared at matched nominal levels. MLOD and MLOQ were estimated from the variability of low-level responses in combination with the calibration slope, using replicate injections at several levels (0.5–50 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$) (Table S5 in SI-1). Accuracy was assessed as matrix-spike recovery by fortifying the matrices at 25 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$ in triplicates and quantifying with labelled standards used for samples (Table S6 in SI-1). Additionally, in the recovery tests (experiments without sorbent, shaken for 24 h), recovery were calculated by comparing the measured concentrations after equilibration with the nominal spiked concentrations in blank matrices, and ranged from 95 to 104 %, indicating no significant analyte loss during the test (Table S8 in SI-1).

3. Results and discussion

The sorption isotherms of the studied pharmaceuticals in the two soils (Spanish soil (SS) and Finnish soil (FS)), the four BBFs (ash-based BBF, ADC; plant-based BBF, BAI; animal byproduct-based BBF, OG2; and manure-based BBF, FEK), the SS amended with four BBFs (SA, SB, SO, and SF), and the FS amended with the four BBFs (FA, FB, FO, and FF) are shown in Figures S1–S4, respectively. Sorption of the pharmaceuticals was fitted to the Freundlich model with R^2 values ranging from 0.80 to 0.98 in the two unamended soils (Table S9), from 0.73 to 1.0 in the four BBFs (Table S10), from 0.90 to 0.99 (Table S11) in the amended SS, and from 0.93 to 1.0 (Table S12) in amended FS. The Freundlich sorption coefficients, K_f , which reflect the affinities of each compound to soils and BBFs, are also listed in Table S9–S10 and Figure S1–S4, as well

as the n values derived from Freundlich equations. Additionally, K_d values (representing linear sorption with NRMSE (defined in section 2.4) of 0.04–0.25) are also shown in Table S7–S10 and Figure S5. It is evident from Figure S1–S4 and Table S9–S12 that the sorption of the studied pharmaceuticals (K_d and K_f values) was dependent on the types of pharmaceuticals, soils, and BBFs.

The four studied pharmaceuticals are weakly acidic, with pK_a values ranging from 3.9 to 4.9 (naproxen: 4.2; diclofenac: 4.2; furosemide: 3.9; ibuprofen: 4.9) in Table S1, which are lower than the pH of the soils, BBFs and amended soils (e.g. pH = 7.5 in SS and pH = 6.5 in FS; Table S3). Therefore, the studied pharmaceutical molecules were predominantly present in anionic forms under the experimental conditions in this study. It is important to note that K_f values is not an independent parameter, but is intrinsically influenced by the Freundlich exponent n . Since K_f is derived from empirical fitting and its units depend on the value of n , comparisons of K_f values across compounds or matrices with different n values can be misleading and lack physical consistency (Xu et al., 2009). We observed considerable variations in n values for the same compound across different samples, as well as significant differences in n values among different pharmaceuticals in the same sample. Consequently, relying on K_f values to describe sorption capacity could compromise the accuracy of sorption assessments and subsequent modeling. Therefore, K_d values were employed in further analysis.

3.1. Sorption behavior of pharmaceuticals in soils

The linear sorption coefficient (K_d defined in section 2.4), calculated as the average of all data points (Table S8 and Figure S5), provides a more suitable means to describe sorption behavior in soil as it offers a higher level of tolerance than K_f (Carballa et al., 2008; Chen et al., 2017; Xu et al., 2009). The mean K_d values of the studied pharmaceuticals followed the order: ibuprofen < naproxen < furosemide < diclofenac in both SS and FS (Table 1 and Figure S5). Furthermore, these four compounds exhibited higher sorption affinity in FS (6.1–20.1 L/kg) than in SS (3.3–8.4 L/kg) in Table 1. This trend is consistent with previous studies reporting that anionic pharmaceuticals and pesticides generally exhibit weak sorption in neutral to weakly acidic soils or in river sediments, often with K_d values below 10 L/kg (Durán-Álvarez et al., 2012; Hiller and Šebesta, 2017; Li et al., 2020). For example, naproxen showed a K_d of 4.41 L/kg in agricultural soils (Durán-Álvarez et al., 2012). Many anionic compounds, such as ibuprofen and naproxen, exhibited higher K_d values in soils with higher OMC as organic matter provides additional sites for the interactions (e.g., hydrogen bonds and hydrophobic interactions). Additionally, lower pH leads to a higher sorption affinity for anionic compounds (Kodešová et al., 2015). Therefore, higher sorption affinities observed in FS likely reflect its lower pH and higher OMC

Table 1
Sorption isotherm parameters of four pharmaceuticals in SS and FS.

Compounds	SS					
	$K_f \pm \text{CI}$ (95 %), ($\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$) \times ($\text{L}/\mu\text{g}$) ⁿ	$n \pm \text{CI}$ (95 %)	R^{2b}	Average K_d (range), L/kg	NRMSE ^b	D_{ow}^a
Naproxen	1.17 \pm 0.67	1.17 \pm 1.12	0.80	3.4 (2.4–4.6)	0.13	0.63
Diclofenac	2.00 \pm 1.76	1.16 \pm 0.98	0.95	8.4 (4.6–16.3)	0.07	14.5
Furosemide	0.42 \pm 0.38	1.34 \pm 1.02	0.90	3.6 (2.8–4.0)	0.15	0.03
Ibuprofen	1.54 \pm 1.12	1.07 \pm 1.02	0.95	3.3 (2.6–4.3)	0.05	23.9
FS						
Naproxen	6.13 \pm 1.21	0.60 \pm 0.43	0.98	12.1 (6.9–20.5)	0.27	6.3
Diclofenac	3.78 \pm 1.99	1.29 \pm 1.37	0.94	20.1 (14.8–27.1)	0.11	143.9
Furosemide	3.26 \pm 1.12	1.28 \pm 0.33	0.95	16.9 (12.9–22.1)	0.18	0.27
Ibuprofen	0.25 \pm 0.21	1.42 \pm 0.76	0.93	6.1 (4.8–8.8)	0.07	233.9

^a Log D_{ow} (pH-dependent octanol-water distribution ratio) is calculated by formula <https://www.ecetoc.org/technical-report-123/estimated-partitioning-property-data/computational-methods/logdow/>; SS: Spanish soil; FS: Finnish soil.

^b The value is from Freundlich model; K_d : soil-water sorption coefficients; K_f : Freundlich capacity coefficient; Soil–water sorption coefficient: $K_d = C_s/C_w$, where C_s represents the concentration in soil solids; C_w is the concentration in aqueous solution. n : dimensionless isotherm curvature. NRMSE: normalized root mean squared error; CI: Confidence interval.

(Table S7) compared with SS (Table 1).

3.2. Sorption behavior of pharmaceuticals in BBFs

The K_d values in four BBFs were in the order: ADC < FEK < OG2 < BA1 for all four chemicals. The higher pH level in ADC (pH 10.5; Table S7) in comparison to SS (pH 7.5; Table S7) and FS (pH 6.5; Table S7) resulted in lower sorption affinities of anionic compounds for ADC. It is noteworthy that the sorption of chemicals onto minerals in ADC (Table S10 and Figure S5) may be weaker compared to their interaction with the comparatively high amount of organic matter in SS and FS (Kodešová et al., 2015). Therefore, K_d values for diclofenac (6.2 L/kg; Table S10 and Figure S5), naproxen (2.1 L/kg; Table S10 and Figure S5), furosemide (1.4 L/kg; Table S10 and Figure S5), and ibuprofen (1.8 L/kg; Table S10 and Figure S5) in ADC are lower than those in SS (8.4 L/kg for diclofenac, 3.4 L/kg for naproxen, 3.6 L/kg for furosemide, and 3.3 L/kg for ibuprofen; Table 1 and Figure S5) and FS (20.1 L/kg for diclofenac, 12.1 L/kg for naproxen, 16.9 L/kg for furosemide, and 6.1 L/kg for ibuprofen; Table S9 and Figure S5).

The OMC in FEK (68 %; Table S7) considerably exceeded that in SS (3.5 %; Table S7) and FS (6.6 %; Table S7) and the pH in FEK (6.5 in Table S7) was higher than that of SS (7.5 in Table S7) and was the same as in FS (6.5 in Table S7). The K_d values for the four chemicals (11.2–44.2 L/kg; Table S10 and Figure S5) in FEK were observed to be higher than those in FS (6.1–20.1 L/kg; Figure S5). This discrepancy can be attributed to the likely disparity in OMC between FEK and FS. Consequently, this difference in OMC resulted in stronger sorption in FEK. The OMC in OG2 (95 % in Table S7) surpassed that in BA1 (93 % in Table S7), while the pH in OG2 (5.5) (Table S7) exceeded that in BA1 (4.6) (Table S7). Therefore, this difference in pH was found to have a more pronounced effect on sorption affinity than the variance in OMC for these compounds. The average K_d values in BA1 ranged from 79.1 to 473.4 L/kg, representing a higher sorption affinity than OG2 in which the K_d values ranged from 32.6 to 377.2 L/kg. Therefore, the influence of pH and OMC on sorption of compounds should both be considered, as the addition of BBFs caused change in pH and OMC in soil.

3.3. The influence of BBFs on the sorption of pharmaceuticals in soil

It was observed that the sorption affinity for these four compounds followed the sequence SA (Spanish soil with ashed BBF) < SF (Spanish soil with FEK) < SO (Spanish soil with OG2) < SB (Spanish soil with BA1) in the amended Spanish soils and K_d values ranged from 1.7 to 9.5 L/kg, 5.1–20.2 L/kg, 13.4–32.4 L/kg, and 15.4–32.7 L/kg, respectively, as shown in Table S11 and Figure S5. The addition of ADC to SS (SA) led to a decrease of the OMC from 3.5 % to 3.3 % and an increase in the pH

from 7.5 to 8.3, as indicated in Table S7. This increase in pH and decrease in OMC had the effect of reducing the sorption affinity in *SS* amended with *ADC* (*SA*). Consequently, the K_d values of the four compounds were found to be lower in *SA* (ranging from 1.7 to 9.5 L/kg; Table S11 and Figure S5) compared to *SS* (ranging from 3.3 to 8.4 L/kg; Figure S5). When *BA1*, *OG2*, and *FEK* were added to *SS* separately, K_d values for these four compounds increased. These values notably surpassed those in *SS* (ranging from 3.3 to 8.4 L/kg; Figure S5) due to lower pH and higher OMC. The sorption affinity for different compounds followed a new order: ibuprofen < furosemide < naproxen < diclofenac in *SA*, ibuprofen < naproxen < furosemide < diclofenac in *SB* and *SF*, whereas it was ibuprofen < naproxen < diclofenac < furosemide in *SO*, which is in contrast to the sorption affinity order observed in *SS*. Despite the OMC being slightly lower in *SB* (8.2; Table S7) than in *SO* (8.3; Table S7), the pH difference between 6.8 in *SB* and 7.2 in *SO*, as depicted in Table S7, likely led to a higher K_d value (32.7 L/kg for diclofenac; Figure S5) in *SB* compared to *SO* (28.6 L/kg for diclofenac; Figure S5). A similar phenomenon was observed with naproxen and ibuprofen, exhibiting a higher K_d value (24.1 L/kg for naproxen and 15.4 L/kg for ibuprofen; Figure S5) in *SB* compared to *SO* (14.9 L/kg for naproxen and 13.4 L/kg for ibuprofen; Figure S5). However, furosemide had a lower K_d value in *SB* than that in *SO*. This indicates that fluctuations in OMC had a more significant impact on K_d than fluctuations in pH did for furosemide.

The K_d values for amended Finnish soil (10.0–23.9 L/kg in *FA* (Finnish soil with ashed BBF), 18.9–74.1 L/kg in *FB* (Finnish soil with *BA1*), 18.7–49.0 L/kg in *FO* (Finnish soil with *OG2*), and 8.9–32.0 L/kg in *FF* (Finnish soil with *FEK*) in Figure S5 and Table S12) varied more and are typically higher than those in amended *SS*. This increase is attributed to changes in pH and OMC due to the introduction of the BBFs. Similarly, naproxen, diclofenac, furosemide, and ibuprofen exhibited higher K_d values in *FB* compared to *FO*, with furosemide showing a notably higher K_d value in *FB* than in *FO*.

In summary, both pH and OMC significantly impacted the sorption of the four anionic compounds tested in both soils. BBFs that are rich in organic matter increased the sorption affinity of studied compounds whereas ashed BBFs weakened the sorption capacity of the tested pharmaceuticals in soil. In the following paragraph, the question which factor caused by BBFs, pH, or OMC, exerts a greater influence on the adsorption capacity of each pharmaceutical in soil is further explored.

3.4. Modelling the sorption of four pharmaceuticals: the influence of pH and OMC

Because the units of the Freundlich coefficient (K_f) depend on the exponent n —and n varies among studied soils (Table S9 and Table S11–S13)— K_f lacks cross-soil comparability and is therefore unsuitable for developing a unified sorption model. Accordingly, we used the linear distribution coefficient K_d to characterize sorption (Eq. (1) in Section 2.5). After comparing alternative functional forms, the specification $f(D_{ow}) = \text{linear model}$ and $f(\text{OMC}) = \text{power}$ performed best for all four pharmaceuticals (test-set $R^2 = 0.86\text{--}0.95$; NRMSE = 0.04–0.10; see Table S11–S14). The fitted parameters are reported in Eqs. (2)–(5). The coefficient on the D_{ow} term (denoted a) has units of L/kg and represents the effective capacity/affinity of the soil's hydrophobic domain toward the neutral species (different compounds can exhibit different affinities; Eqs (2)–(5)). The coefficient on the OMC term (denoted b) has units of L/kg and represents the strength of OMC-mediated interactions with the anionic species; an exponent $c > 1$ indicates a super-linear OMC effect, consistent with cooperative mechanisms in the organic matter domain, e.g., micropore filling, cation bridging, hydrogen bonding (Alhalabi et al., 2024). To elucidate the effects of pH and OMC, we computed normalized sensitivity indices (NSI; Section 2.5) and constructed dominance maps, where the dominance ratio is defined as $|\text{NSI}_{\text{OMC}}| / (|\text{NSI}_{\text{pH}}| + |\text{NSI}_{\text{OMC}}|)$ (values < 0.5 indicate pH dominance; values > 0.5 indicate OMC dominance) in Fig. 1. NSI_{pH} is predominantly

Fig. 1. Normalized sensitivity index (NSI) contour plots for four pharmaceuticals (Naproxen, Ibuprofen, Diclofenac, and Furosemide) with respect to pH and organic matter content (OMC). NSI with respect to pH (NSI_{pH}); NSI with respect to OMC (NSI_{OMC}); the dominant sensitivity factor, expressed as $\text{NSI}_{\text{pH}}/(\text{NSI}_{\text{pH}} + \text{NSI}_{\text{OMC}})$; Black rectangles indicate the dataset ranges of pH and OMC for each compound.

Fig. 2. Ionized and neutral fractions of four acidic pharmaceuticals (Ibuprofen, Diclofenac, Naproxen, and Furosemide) in the range of soil pH.

negative, i.e., lower pH increases sorption (K_d), whereas NSI_{OMC} is positive, i.e., higher OMC increases sorption (Fig. 1). Within the dataset ranges (see section 2.5), they show large $|NSI_{pH}|$ under acidic to near-neutral and low-OMC conditions, specifically at $pH \leq 6.5$ – 7.0 and $OMC \leq 8$ – 10 %, where the dominance ratio is < 0.5 (Fig. 1). This means small pH shifts can produce pronounced changes in K_d . Mechanistically, at low pH range, the compounds retain a substantial neutral fraction variation. For example, for ibuprofen ($pK_a = 4.9$), the neutral fraction is 44.3 % at $pH = 5.0$ and 20.1 % at $pH = 5.5$. Their sorption is dominated by hydrophobic partitioning to SOM (Zhang et al., 2017). Changes in the neutral fraction (captured through D_{ow}) largely control K_d , whereas the OMC-dependent pathway contributes relatively little. Consequently, $|NSI_{pH}|$ is large while NSI_{OMC} is small. In localized high-pH/high-OMC zones—about $pH \geq 7.0$ – 7.5 with $OMC \geq 6$ – 10 %, NSI_{OMC} increases and the dominance shifts to OMC. At high pH, the acids are predominantly anionic and hydrophobic partitioning becomes negligible; Fe/Al oxides are mostly negatively charged, so sorption (if any) is more sensitivity on OMC-related interactions such as cation bridging, hydrogen bonding, and polar/ π - π interactions (Alhalabi et al., 2024). Beyond the dataset range (e.g., $pH > 8.5$ or $OMC > 12.2$ %), empirical validation is lacking; nonetheless, model projections suggest that $|NSI_{pH}|$ remains appreciable, while NSI_{OMC} increases modestly. Notably, part of the apparent pH effect may operate through changes in the surface-charge density of soil organic matter at higher pH, rather than shifts in the neutral fraction (Milne et al., 2001). Because our model lacks an explicit metal-oxide sorption term, scenarios with extremely low OMC and low pH (e.g., less than 1 %)—where a considerable fraction of furosemide remains ionized (56 % anionic at pH 4) and oxide surfaces can be positively charged, likely entail non-negligible sorption to mineral phases (Alhalabi et al., 2024; Fabregat-Palau et al., 2024; Zhang et al., 2017). Therefore, any pH variation induced by soil management practices such as BBF application or irrigation could substantially alter the sorption dynamics of these pharmaceuticals in soil. This suggests that in atypical soil scenarios—such as those affected by alkaline irrigation or rich in humic substances—OMC could play a more substantial role. Nevertheless, in most agricultural soils and practical management, pH is likely to remain the key driver of the environmental behavior of naproxen, diclofenac, and ibuprofen.

4. Conclusion

This study investigated the sorption behavior of four pharmaceuticals (ibuprofen, naproxen, furosemide, and diclofenac) in soils and soils amended with bio-based fertilizers (BBFs). K_d values of the studied pharmaceuticals exhibited a strong dependence on both pH and organic matter, which resulted in different adsorption behavior in these matrices. To further disentangle the relative contributions of pH and organic matter to pharmaceutical sorption, a normalized sensitivity index (NSI) approach was applied. Their sorption was more sensitive to changes in pH at low pH level and low OMC. In contrast, under neutral to alkaline conditions, OMC dominated sorption. This indicates that changes induced by BBF amendments—particularly simultaneous shifts in pH and OMC—can exert diverse effects on pharmaceutical behavior in soil. However, this study did not account for concentration effects or sorption to metal oxides. Future research should therefore incorporate a broader set of soil characteristics to enable a more comprehensive understanding of the multifactorial controls governing pharmaceutical sorption, mobility, and persistence in complex soil systems.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Yan Dong: Writing – original draft, Validation, Methodology, Conceptualization. **John R. Parsons:** Supervision. **Antonia Praetorius:** Supervision. **Eva de Rijke:** Supervision. **J. Chris Slootweg:** Supervision. **Boris Jansen:** Supervision.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envres.2025.123092>.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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